

Synthesis, structural and electrical studies of cobalt-, nickel-, copper- and zinc(II) polymeric complexes

P. J. Bahad^a, N. S. Bhav^b and A. S. Aswar^{*a}

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Amravati University, Amravati-444 602, India

^bDepartment of Chemistry, Nagpur University, Nagpur-440 010, India

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The polymeric complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} with Schiff base ligands bis(2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone)-1,3-diaminopropane and bis(2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone)-1,3-diaminopropane (H₂L¹/H₂L²) have been prepared. The ligands acts as bisbidentate molecule. The kinetic parameters for their decomposition have been evaluated by graphical Freeman-Carroll and Sharp-Wentworth equations from TG data. The values of kinetic and thermodynamic parameters are comparable and that the decomposition follows a common reaction mode. DC electrical conductivity of the chelates has been studied in the temperature range 300–520 K.

Schiff bases containing polyfunctional groups offer many practical advantages and unique structural environments for complexation¹. In continuation of our studies and with a view to investigate the ligating behaviour of H₂L¹ and H₂L², we have undertaken the synthetic and structural studies of Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} polymeric complexes of Schiff bases derived from substituted acetophenones and 1,3-diaminopropane

Results and Discussion

All the chelates are coloured and insoluble in water and common organic solvents, indicating their polymeric nature². Elemental analysis suggest 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) stoichiometry.

The ligand IR band at 2915–2935 cm⁻¹ due to intramolecular hydrogen bonded phenolic OH stretch of the ligands, disappeared in the spectra of the polychelates indicating deprotonation of OH and subsequent coordination of oxygen with metal ions³. The strong band around 1610 cm⁻¹ (central C=N) and negative shift by 15–25 cm⁻¹ observed in all the polychelates indicate participation of the azomethine nitrogen in chelate formation. The positive shift of the ligand band at ~1290 cm⁻¹ (phenolic C–O) by 20–40 cm⁻¹ in the polychelates indicates participation of phenolic oxygen in coordination, subsequent to deprotonation⁴. New bands observed at 400–550 cm⁻¹ are assigned to

M–N and M–O modes⁵, confirming coordination through the deprotonation phenolic oxygen and azomethine nitrogen. The band at 3300–3600 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the polychelates may be due to the OH vibration of coordinated water molecules. The polychelates also exhibited bands at around 770–790 and 1580 cm⁻¹ which are assigned to coordinated water⁶

Magnetic moment values (Table 1) provide evidence for the high-spin octahedral configuration for Co^{II} complexes. The Cu^{II} complexes are paramagnetic and the magnetic moments correspond to one unpaired electron⁷. The Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic indicating square-planar and tetrahedral geometries, respectively.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of polychelates

Compd	Metal % Found/(Calcd)	μ_{eff}	σ	τ
		B M	Ω cm ⁻¹	eV
[CoL ¹ (H ₂ O) ₂] _n	13.08 (13.66)	4.96	2.22×10^7	0.318
[CoL ² (H ₂ O) ₂] _n	12.12 (12.48)	4.79	3.22×10^7	0.085
{[NiL ¹](H ₂ O)} _n	14.00 (14.20)	Dia	1.11×10^8 ^b	0.287
[NiL ²] _n	13.13 (13.46)	Dia	6.89×10^{10}	0.166
{[CuL ¹](2H ₂ O)} _n	14.22 (14.57)	1.71	2.35×10^9	0.235
{[CuL ²](2H ₂ O)} _n	13.02 (13.31)	1.84	6.99×10^8 ^b	0.126
{[ZnL ¹](2H ₂ O)} _n	14.75 (14.57)	Dia	3.36×10^8 ^b	0.166
{[ZnL ²](2H ₂ O)} _n	13.33 (13.64)	Dia	7.60×10^7	0.358

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses

The electronic spectra of the Co^{II} polychelates show three *d-d* absorption bands at 9530–9570, 17705–17793 and 20120–21090 cm⁻¹ assignable to ⁴T_{1g}(F) → ⁴T_{2g}(F).

${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ transitions, respectively, in conformity with octahedral stereochemistry around Co^{II} ion⁸. The two bands observed in each of the Ni^{II} chelates at 17750–18000 and 23950–24000 cm^{-1} may be assigned to the transition arising from ${}^1A_{1g}$ ground state to ${}^1B_{2g}$ and ${}^1B_{1g}$ excited state, respectively⁹. A broad band observed in both the Cu^{II} polychelates at 14400–16370 cm^{-1} may be attributed to the $d-d$ transition ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$, indicating planar stereochemistry¹⁰. The appearance of the bands near the visible region indicates the complex to be square-planar. As expected the electronic spectra of the Zn^{II} polychelates do not furnish any relevant information towards stereochemistry but on the basis of the elemental and IR studies, tetrahedral geometry is suggested for these polychelates¹¹. The magnetic susceptibility values (Table 1) indicate that the Co^{II} and Cu^{II} chelates are paramagnetic and spin-free whereas the Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} chelates are diamagnetic and spin-paired.

All the pyrolysis curves behave similarly and decompose in a two-stage process. The elimination of two lattice water molecules takes place around 140° per $\text{Cu}^{II}/\text{Zn}^{II}$ atom and one water molecule per $\text{Ni}^{II}\text{-H}_2\text{L}^1$ chelate. The Co^{II} chelates show removal of two water molecules above 150°, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules per repeating unit¹². The $\text{Ni}^{II}\text{-H}_2\text{L}^2$ chelate is stable upto 290° and decomposes in a single step upto 600° leaving a

residue of the metal oxide. The thermogravimetric studies agree well with the mass-loss data obtained in independent pyrolysis experiments. From the initial decomposition temperatures (Table 2), the relative thermal stabilities of the polychelates were deduced : $\text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu} > \text{Zn}$. The graphical Freeman-Carroll¹³ and Sharp-Wentworth¹⁴ methods were used to calculate kinetic parameters (Table 2). The degradation of the polychelates is a complex process as noted from the non-integer order of reaction¹⁵. In addition, the thermodynamic parameters such as entropy change (ΔS), free energy change (ΔF), apparent entropy change (S^*) and frequency factor (Z) have also been calculated using transition state theory. The similarity in the values of thermodynamic parameters indicates that the basic steps involved in the thermal degradation of the polychelates are the same¹⁶. The ΔS values for all the polychelates are negative, which indicates that the activated complex has a more ordered structure than the reactants and that the reactions are slower than normal¹⁷.

The DC electrical conductivity of polychelates were measured in pellet form in the temperature range 300–510 K. In the electrical conduction domain, the temperature dependence of the electrical conductivity obeys the equation¹⁸, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(-E_a/kT)$, the symbol having the usual meaning. The values of electrical conductivity (σ) and ac-

Fig. 1. Temperature dependence of log σ

Table 2. Thermal data of polychelates

Compd.	Decomp temp. °C	E		-ΔS J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔF kJ mol ⁻¹	-S° kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	Z S ⁻¹	n
		kJ mol ⁻¹						
		FC ^a	SW ^b					
CoL ¹	320	16.49	18.34	289.20	106.92	0.095	143.49	0.61
CoL ²	310	15.13	19.38	296.64	107.88	0.098	151.12	0.75
NiL ¹	300	23.40	33.96	308.61	119.99	0.102	304.00	0.75
NiL ²	290	17.48	20.13	312.29	115.22	0.110	49.94	0.85
CuL ¹	260	27.21	36.78	300.62	121.34	0.102	384.69	0.75
CuL ²	280	28.42	30.67	307.60	124.60	0.109	350.40	0.85
ZnL ¹	250	17.14	20.34	304.23	112.34	0.108	67.06	0.82
ZnL ²	230	16.48	19.12	293.63	108.26	0.100	65.18	0.75

^aFC = Freeman-Carroll. ^bSW = Sharp-Wentworth

tivation energy are listed in Table 1. In all cases, the conductivity increased with increasing temperature indicating that these chelates lie in the range of semiconductors¹⁹. It can be seen from the plots (Fig. 1) that there are two distinct regions. In the low temperature region, the slopes of plots have small values and the polymers may present extrinsic conduction. In the high temperature region, a linear dependence of $\log \sigma = F(1/T)$ is observed. In this temperature domain the polymers may present intrinsic conduction²⁰. The lower temperature range is the region of extrinsic semiconductors where the conduction is due to the excitation of carriers from donor localized level to the conduction band. At the higher temperature range, the intrinsic region is reached where carriers are thermally activated from the valence band to the conduction band²¹. The conductivity of the chelates at 373 K follows the following order : Co^{II} > Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} and Zn^{II} > Co^{II} > Cu^{II} > Ni^{II}, while the activation energy declines as Co^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} > Zn^{II} and Zn^{II} > Ni^{II} > Cu^{II} > Co^{II} for H₂L¹ and H₂L², respectively. The conductivity values of all the polychelates of H₂L² except Ni^{II} at room temperature were found to be higher than those of H₂L¹ polychelates and this may be due to the presence of chloro group. The small activation energy observed may be attributed to the interaction between the electrons of *d*-orbitals of the cations and the π -orbitals of the ligand. This interaction will localize the π -electronic charge on the ligand molecule²². We also reported such small activation energy (0.102–0.872 eV) for polyschiff base chelates²³.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The solvents used were purified by standard methods²⁴. The ligands bis(2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone)-1,3-diaminopropane (H₂L¹) and bis(2-hydroxy-5-chloroacetophenone)-1,3-diaminopropane (H₂L²) were obtained (yield

70%) by Schiff base condensation of the appropriate ketone (0.02 mol) with 1,3-diaminopropane (0.01 mol) in ethanolic solution. The purity of the ligands was checked by TLC, m.p. 110 and 140°.

A hot DMF-ethanol (0.01 mol in 25 ml) solution of the hydrated metal acetate (chloride for Zn^{II}) was added dropwise with stirring, to an ethanolic solution of the respective ligand (0.01 mol in 25 ml) until the metal-to-ligand ratio reached 1 : 1 and the content was refluxed for 2–3 h. After cooling, the resulting solid complexes were washed with water followed by ethanol and acetone and dried over calcium chloride under reduced pressure.

C, H and N analyses were performed at Microanalytical Section, C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The metals were estimated by oxide method. Magnetic susceptibility was measured with a Gouy's set-up at room temperature using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as calibrating agent and calculations were made using computed values of Pascal's constants. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Nicolet Magna IR 550 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a PAS spectrophotometer at Radiochemistry Division, B.A.R.C., Trombay. TGA study was carried out on a Perkin-Elmer TGS-2 analyzer using Pt-Pt-Rh thermocouple with a heating rate of 10° min⁻¹, in air. The electrical conductivity was measured on a BPL (India) Million-Megohmmeter in pellets form.

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